

ISic1390

Greek funerary(?) inscription of Nikaios

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object

unknown

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-06-14 - Jonathan Prag edited the file in line with edition prepared for Adrano museum catalogue

Place of origin (ancient)

Adranon

Place of origin (modern)

Adrano

Provenance

Described by Gualtherus (1624) as coming from the ruins popularly identified with the shrine of the god Hadranus (not identified). All later editions derive from Gualtherus.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

The stone is one of three described as 'petra nigra' by Gualtherus (1624: 50), but neither state of conservation nor dimensions are recorded.

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

The text is presented as split over three lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plain transcription in standard capitals makes it impossible to assess the letter-forms.

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Νίκαιος

Apparatus

Text from Gualtherus 1624

Translation (en)

Nikaios

Commentary

The stone is presented in the edition of Gualtherus (1624, p.50 nr. 338) under

the same heading as no.4 above, and so the same report appears to apply, namely 'petra nigra', state of conservation and dimensions not recorded; it is said to have come from the ruins popularly equated with the site of the temple of the local divinity Adranos. The text was not included in Torremuzza 1769 or 1784. It is not clear why Kaibel (IG XIV, 571) says 'admodum recens reperta', i.e. only recently recovered.

The name Νίκαιος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%9D%CE%AF%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9%CE%BF%CF%82] is common, although not in Sicily, where there is only one other attested example, probably from Syracuse.

It is impossible to date this text, in the absence of further information, although it is most likely to belong to the Hellenistic period.

Digital identifiers:

TM 493005

PHI 140897

Bibliography

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Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5740

Russo, S. P. 1911. *Illustrazione storico-archeologica di Adernò.* At 59

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